

Analysis of Cascaded H-Bridge Multilevel Solar Inverter

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Abstract:

Inverter used to convert Direct Current (DC) into Alternating current (AC), at first the working of basic H-bridge single phase inverter explained, which is carry forward with the explanation of cascaded H-bridge inverter. There are two linear transformers are used in design of Cascaded H Bridge solar inverter which is described in block diagram of standalone inverter model. This successfully implemented in MATLAB and Simulink results of load voltage, load current, both linear transformer voltage waveforms, and grid voltage with respect to time has shown in this paper.

Keywords — Cascaded H bridge, Standalone Inverter, Solar Energy, Total Harmonic Distortion.

I. INTRODUCTION

Single-phase H-bridge inverter is composed of two inverter legs with two IGBT devices in each leg. The inverter dc bus voltage V_d is usually fixed, while its ac output voltage V_{ab} can be adjusted by either bipolar or unipolar modulation schemes. Fig. 1 shows a simplified circuit diagram of a single-phase H-bridge inverter.

Fig. 1 Single phase H-Bridge Inverter

The cascaded H-bridge multilevel inverter uses multiple units of H-bridge power cells connected in a series chain to produce high ac voltages. A typical configuration of a seven-level CHB Inverter is shown in Fig. 2, where each phase leg consists of three H-bridge cells powered by three isolated dc supplies of equal voltage E .

Fig. 2 Per-phase diagram of seven-level CHB inverters

The total number of active switches (IGBTs) used in the CHB inverters can be calculated by;

$$N_{sw} = 6 (m - 1)$$

An m -level CHB inverter using level-shifted multi-

Carrier modulation scheme requires $(m - 1)$ triangular carriers, all having the same frequency and amplitude.

The $(m - 1)$ triangular carriers are vertically disposed such that the bands they occupy are contiguous. The frequency modulation index is given by $m_f = f_{cr} / f_m$, which remains the same as that for the phase-shifted modulation scheme.

Whereas the amplitude modulation index is defined as;

$$m_a = \frac{\hat{V}_m}{\hat{V}_{cr}(m-1)} \quad \text{for } 0 \leq m_a \leq 1$$

Here, V_m is the peak amplitude of the modulating wave V_m and V_{cr} is the peak amplitude of each carrier wave.

In this work, since each secondary of both transformers is connected in series [13]. Fig. 3 shows block diagram of Cascaded H Bridge solar standalone inverter with linear transformer

Fig. 3 Cascaded H Bridge solar standalone inverter with linear transformer

The output voltage becomes the instantaneous sum of secondary voltage of both transformers, as given in equation

$$V_{out} = \sum_{n=0}^{k-1} 3^n V_{n+1} = V_1 + 3V_2$$

Number of voltage levels at the output is determined by equation.

$$N = 3^k$$

Here, k means the number of transformers, which have a turn-ratio of the power of three in sequence. V_n can be E , 0 , or $-E$; therefore, V_{out} can produce $-4E$, $-3E$, $-2E$, $-E$, 0 , E , $2E$, $3E$, $4E$ by mixing of each secondary voltage of the transformers. The number switches become less in this topology as compare to level shifted cascaded H bridge inverter. As we have got nine levels with two h bridge inverter here in

compare to three as got in LSM seven level inverter. Thus no. of level is improved, while decreasing no. of H bridges in cascaded transformer topology.

II. MATLAB IMPLEMENTATION

Here first we have implemented the PWM fed stand-alone cascaded multilevel inverter in MATLAB as shown in Fig.4. Where inside cascaded inverter block, we implemented the cascaded MLI with two linear transformers as shown in Fig.6. Here,

1. E0 is the DC Supply source of 200 volt for both h bridge inverters.

2. Two linear transformers of 75 KVA, 50 Hz, 325 Vrms in cascaded form.
3. Single phase R load of 3 kilo watt.

Next is PWM block shown enlarged view in Fig.5 which generates the pulses for MLI. Where,

1. Modulation index is 0.8, Frequency is 50 Hz.
2. Both the reference sine wave having 60-degree phase difference.

Further in place of DC source we have use solar panel with LC filter as $L = 70$ milli henry and $C = 10$ micro farad as shown in Fig.7.

Fig.4 Cascaded PWM Fed Nine level inverter in MATLAB

Fig.5 PWM switching scheme in cascaded MLI

Fig. 6 Standalone Multilevel Inverter using linear transformer with R load

Fig.7 Cascaded Grid tied Multilevel Solar Inverter using linear transformer with R load

III. SIMULINK RESULTS

When we run model as shown in fig.6, we got nine level cascaded inverter's load voltage as shown in fig.8.

Fig.8: Nine level cascaded inverter's Load voltage v/s Time waveform

Both linear transformer voltage waveforms are shown in fig.9 and fig.10 respectively

Fig.9 Voltage of First Transformer v/s Time waveform

Further the model as shown in fig.7 using single Phase 230 Vrms, 50 Hz grid produce the load voltage and current as shown in fig.11. The THD is 5.65 percent. This is decreased as compare to simple solar fed H bridge inverter.

Fig.10: Voltage of Second Transformer v/s Time waveform

Fig .11 various voltages and current of Grid connected cascaded Solar MLI

CONCLUSIONS

In normal condition inverter current T.H.D is under the limit, also improved by using cascaded H-Bridge with linear transformers. These multilevel inverters reduce the total harmonic distortion (THD) in the output waveform of the inverter without reducing the output voltage quality. This paper successfully implemented MATLAB and Simulink results of load voltage, load current, both linear transformer voltage waveforms, and grid voltage with respect to time.

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